

Impact of Quality Assurance Mechanisms on the Work Efficiency of Staff in the Educational Space of Georgia

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Abstract—At this stage, Georgia is a country which is actively involved in the European integration process, for which the primary priority is effective integration in the European education system. The modern Georgian higher education system is the process of establishing a new sociocultural reality, whose main priorities are determined by the Quality System as a continuous cycle of planning, implementation, checking and acting. Obviously, in this situation, the issue of management of education institutions comes out in the foreground, since the proper planning and implementation of personnel management processes is one of the main determinants of the company's performance. At the same time, one of the most important factors is the psychological comfort of the personnel, ensuring their protection and efficiency of stress management policy. The purpose of this research is to determine how intensely the relationship is between the psychological comfort of the personnel and the efficiency of the quality system in the institution as the quality assurance mechanisms of educational institutions affect the stability of personnel, prevention and management of the stressful situation. The research was carried out within the framework of the Internal Grant Project «The Role of Organizational Culture in the Process of Settlement of Management of Stress and Conflict, Georgian Reality and European Experience » of the Batumi Navigation Teaching University, based on the analysis of the survey results of target groups. The small-scale research conducted by us has revealed that the introduction of quality assurance system and its active implementation increased the quality of management of Georgian educational institutions, increased the level of universal engagement in internal and external processes and as a result, it has improved the quality of education as well as social and psychological comfort indicators of the society.

Keywords—Quality assurance, effective management, stability of personnel, psychological comfort, stress management.

I. INTRODUCTION

EDUCATION is one of the fundamental rights of a human being and a prominent meaning for the country's sustainable development. Consequently, the quality and

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accessibility of education and science system should be one of the main priorities of the country's development [1].

13-year process of the introduction of European Standards of Quality in Georgia's education system showed us clearly, that the quality of the educational institution represents the sum of complex analysis of the quality of the ongoing processes in the institution. Among them, the most important is - control of the quality of staff satisfaction and ensure continuous cycle of its improvement. Any, including the right management of an educational institution, is the cornerstone of its correct quality.

The goal of the research is to determine whether the quality of the management of institutions and in particular, the quality of personnel management and support system has been increased together with the introduction of quality assurance system.

Whether or not the enactment of quality control systems influenced to activate the fight against stress, increased the level of psychological comfort of teachers and staff and as a result – increased quality of their performance.

II. METHODOLOGY

Both general and specific research methods are used in this article, namely - the methods of analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, scientific abstraction, comparative analysis, statistics (selection, grouping, observation, dynamics, etc.), static, as well as the methods of experimental evaluation. In order to identify the patterns between the analytical and statistical estimates, the publications of National Agency for Statistics are used.

III. DISCUSSION

It is noteworthy that at the moment of introduction of quality assurance system in Georgian educational space, the country has radically changed course and after a long period of stagnation, it began to implement complex systematic reforms aimed at improving the quality of teaching and learning processes, which are still continuing and after completion, it will ensure the full implementation of Georgia in the World Education Space.

It is a widely recognized fact that the main way to increase the efficiency of the company is that the goals and values of the company are understood by the company staff [2]. The employees of the organization based on this principle are better acquainted with the goals and objectives, current

success and problems. Most importantly, this type of staff is a strong source of ideas and provide real ways to develop and improve their activities. That is where the quality system goes through the arena, one of the main goals of which is to ensure continuous improvement of the management system and active involvement of staff in it.

The quality of the organization, rather the quality of the higher education institution is not planning on a specific task, monitoring and performance control. It definitely is in every process. The introduction of quality culture is an integral part of all levels of the organization, and the implementation of its principles – is the primary duty of the management level and the entire staff.

By the example of the world-wide large companies, we can say that universal involvement in all processes of staff is one of the key points of their strategic development plan. Engagement increases staff motivation [3]. Consequently, it affects the essential nature of the processes such as creativity and imagination, innovative ways to combat problems, a sense of growth, stability and professional comfort. All of the above mentioned is the faintest source of stable development of the organization and a high level of competitiveness, as according to the Author (E. Deming) [4] of PDCA Development Continuous Cycle: "All successful researches and initiatives were conducted by people who were happy with their work."

At the target university quality is considered as a system, the unified network of interconnected elements, where each employee is a separate element. The interaction between the elements and their networking functionality is the prerogative of the governing level. Here, it should be emphasized that in this case, the system works on principle of the New Year's Lamp and the less involvement of one element causing all the following elements to be broken down. There are organizational problems that the direct executives are aware of. Very often, the problem arised in local organizational level requires a particular person's response and solving by the managing may become as an irrelevant activity. Consequently, it is necessary to ensure the "involvement" principle, i.e. realization of quality management at all levels, in all subdivisions, with the participation of all employees.

Expert in business ideology and loyalty, author (K. Kharski) [5] of the "Valuable Management Concept" divides companies into three main types: "Circus", "Theater" and "Church". "Circus" provides employees with only food (with enough money for his own) the main motivators in its management are "meat slices" and "thorn", while the main mission of the governing ring is to organize the movement of "tigers" on the arena. Maintaining the illusion of stability and comfort in such an organization is only possible through the fleshy pieces of meat. "Theater" is a company where energy is given to employees through emotions. A good theater always has a strong mainstream director who distributes roles and sees each actor in his/her ideal role on the big stage. He/She stirs the main emotion – pride in the "actors", which becomes the main motivator and energy stimulator. The Third Format - "Church" - is based on the idea, ideology that unites the organization and makes sense of human work. To some extent, it is the

peak of organizational culture, because it always has rules set out in the "holiness" rank, the protection of which is considered as their mission by each employee. Such ideology is based on the greatest cult corporations of modern times - Apple, Microsoft, Google and etc. are based on such ideology.

The University, as a creator, dissemination and establishment center of new knowledge and values, in essence, it should strive to manage the "Church" category management, which is the most actively promoted by the quality system in the Georgian space.

The Quality System as the Main Way of Formation of Organizational Culture

Batumi Navigation Teaching University, based on which our research is conducted, is a private, proficient higher education institution, its staff consists of up to 100 different professions of people and those are consistently placed on the subordinate stairs, they have clearly defined duties and responsibilities. One of the main priorities of the quality assurance system of this University is the formation of the academic community, where every member of the institution feels as an integral part of the institution and believes that it is bound to comply with it.

One of the key priorities of the quality assurance system of the Batumi Navigation Teaching University (research unit) is the establishment of quality culture. It implies in itself a special form of organizational culture, which is based on the norms and values those are fully shared and recognized by the corporate community and their manifestation - relevant organizational behavior.

Process of Implementation of quality culture, as well as organizational culture, consists of two main factors - internal (corporate integration) and external (external adaptation) factors.

Basic elements of organizational culture for higher education institutions are:

- Stereotypes of behavior (common language, sometimes - slang, used by members of the organization; common traditions, rituals, which they necessarily perform together);
- Group norms (samples and standards that determine the actions of the members of the organization);
- Declared values (universally recognized and shared values and principles that are protected and governed by the organization, for example, "quality of produced production");
- "The philosophy of the organization;
- Organizational climate (the spirit, which is determined by the composition of the collective and the characteristic relations between them, which, in turn, determines the rules of communication with external persons).

According to one of the most popular typologies created by the greatest researchers (K. Cameron and R. Kauine), there are four types of criteria, which determine the main value of the organization. these are: 1) Discretion and flexibility; 2) Control and stability; 3) Integration and internal focus; 4) Differentiation and external focus. Dynamic coexistence and

rational use of these criteria determine the continuous pursuit of the organization's growth and perfection [6]-[8].

In the higher education institution, where our research has been conducted, the powerful mechanisms of quality assurance system are implemented. The development of the institution over the last 10 years is implemented in accordance with the strategic plan, which is based on the PDCA principle. The University possesses ISO 9001: 2015 quality certificate and conducts internal and external processes in accordance with the national and international quality requirements. Its organizational culture is part of quality culture and vice versa.

In the course of the study, we conducted the survey of Batumi Navigation Teaching University staff, 96 employees of different levels took part in it; including professors, managers, financial, economic, and administrative staff members. Questions offered by them included the following:

1. Assess your level of satisfaction by working conditions from 1 to 10 by 2005 year;
2. Assess your level of satisfaction by working conditions from 1 to 10 for 2018 year;
3. Assess your social security level by scales from 1 to 10 for the year 2005;
4. Assess your social security level by scales from 1 to 10 for the year 2018;
5. Assess your employer's liability level by scales from 1 to 10 for the year 2005;
6. Assess your employer's liability level by scales from 1 to 10 for the year 2018;
7. Assess the level of psychological comfort associated with the job by scales from 1 to 10 for the year 2005;
8. Assess the level of psychological comfort associated with the job by scales from 1 to 10 for the year 2018;
9. Assess the performance of quality assurance service in your organization by scales from 1 to 10
10. Assess the contribution of the Quality Assurance Service in terms of providing working conditions and creating professional comfort by scales from 1 to 10

Results of the survey are graphically reflected as follows:

Fig. 1 Employee satisfaction according to 2005 data

Fig. 2 Employee satisfaction according to 2018 data

Fig. 3 Assessment of the participation of the Quality Assurance Service by the Employees

The survey revealed that implementation of the quality system and the introduction of the quality culture as the main form of organizational culture, radically changed the attitude of employee to working conditions, feeling of stability, social security, psychosocial comfort issues. The level of satisfaction, with almost all parameters, increased by 50%.

Our research will be continued in other universities in Georgia. However, at this stage, it can be said that after the introduction of education system reform and implementation of quality system, the representatives of the Georgian educational sphere, from the unstable income and socio-psychological risk group, moved firmly in the group of professionals equipped with high honor and corporate spirit, feeling of stability and safety.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The famous formula "98/2" of Deming clearly shows that 98% of the defect of a product or service offered by the organization depending on not the number of ordinary employees, but on the managerial level. In the opinion of the Deming the change of ordinary employees will solve only 2% of the problems, while increasing of the efficiency of management will eliminate the deficit by 98%.

In the 1970s, the philosophy of Deming was resumed by some Japanese followers:

When people and organizations concentrate attention, first of all, on the quality that is determined by the following ratio:

$$\text{Quality} = \frac{\text{Results of work efforts}}{\text{Total costs}}$$

Then, the quality gains the growth trend and shortcomings are decreasing over time.

1) But if people and organizations are concentrated mainly on "defective", the expenses increase over time, while the quality decreases.

The small-scale survey conducted by us has demonstrated that the introduction of the quality assurance system and its active implementation has increased the quality of management of Georgian educational institutions, increased level of universal engagement in internal and external processes - improved the quality of education as well as social and indicators of the psychological comfort of the society.

Finally, we can say that as a result of intensive implementation of the quality system in the field of education, during the last 10 years, the largest part of the organization with "circus" category turned into the „Theater“, where the role of the management level is decisive in the success of the performance, in some cases we got "Church" - the educational hub, where the rules for optimal performance of processes turned into certain "Holiness", the protection of the rule is the obligation of each member of the institution.

The further development of the Quality assurance services and, in general, the quality system is a clear precondition that every educational hub will turn into creator "Temples" of new knowledge and values, which will inevitably work on the creation of competitive product and in the international arena, for establishing the reputation of Georgia as a high-cultural country of management.

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